

Transit Inequality in the Denver Metro Area:

A Quantitative Analysis of Job Accessibility and Service Equity

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Abstract

This study investigates structural inequities in the Denver Regional Transportation District (RTD) network by quantifying job accessibility and service frequency across 664 census tracts. Using General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) data, Longitudinal Employer-Household Dynamics (LODES) employment statistics, and American Community Survey (ACS) demographic estimates, we calculated travel times and reachable jobs for every tract across 18 departure times spanning AM and PM peak periods. After excluding non-residential tracts (leaving 657 residential tracts) and ACS sentinel income values, we find a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.62$) between transit dependency (zero-vehicle households) and job accessibility. Multivariate regression confirms this relationship holds after controlling for population density, CBD distance, and median income ($\beta = 4,318$ jobs per percentage point, $p < 0.001$). Service gaps remain meaningful: 32% of tracts have no nearby service, representing 34% of residents and 13% of zero-vehicle households. Accessibility inequality is substantial (Gini = 0.75), with bottom-income-quartile tracts accessing $6\times$ more jobs than top-quartile tracts.

1 Introduction

Public transportation is a critical determinant of economic mobility. In the Denver metro area, rapid growth has exacerbated housing costs, pushing many lower-income workers to peripheral areas potentially underserved by transit. This study aims to quantify the “spatial mismatch” between affordable housing and job opportunities, specifically examining whether transit-dependent populations face systematic disadvantages in accessing economic centers. We define equity as progressive alignment between access and transit dependency (zero-vehicle share), rather than equal access across all tracts. Because the analysis is cross-sectional, results are descriptive and may reflect residential self-selection as well as service planning.

Contributions

This paper makes the following contributions to the literature on transit equity:

- **Comprehensive accessibility measurement:** We compute job accessibility across 18 departure times (AM and PM peaks) rather than a single snapshot, capturing schedule variability.
- **Multi-method equity assessment:** We combine bivariate correlations, multivariate regression with robust standard errors, and distributional metrics (Gini, quantile comparisons) to characterize equity from multiple angles.
- **Replicable methodology:** All code, data sources, and parameters are documented for full reproducibility. The routing algorithm, origin point selection, and aggregation methods are specified precisely.
- **Separation of alignment from causation:** We explicitly distinguish observed correlation between transit dependency and access from claims about intentional equity targeting, controlling for confounders and discussing alternative explanations.

2 Methodology

We developed a custom Python-based analysis pipeline to model the specific transit landscape of Denver. Full implementation details are provided in a companion technical document; key parameters are summarized below.

2.1 Data Sources

- **Transit Network:** RTD GTFS data (September 2025 schedule), comprising 7,536 stops and 323,000+ scheduled stop times [1].
- **Employment:** Census LODES Workplace Area Characteristics (WAC) data (2021), providing job counts by census block [2].
- **Demographics:** ACS 5-Year Estimates (2018–2022) for income, race, poverty status, and vehicle ownership [3].
- **Geography:** TIGER/Line census tract boundaries (2023) [4].

2.2 Accessibility Calculation

We implemented a connection-scan routing algorithm (similar to RAPTOR) to calculate time-dependent travel times. For each tract, we used a representative interior point and computed the total number of jobs reachable within 30, 45, and 60 minutes. The interior point is computed via Shapely’s `representative_point()` method, which returns a point guaranteed to lie within the

polygon (unlike the centroid, which may fall outside irregular shapes). Accessibility was computed at 18 departure times—every 20 minutes from 6:00–9:00 AM and 3:00–6:00 PM—and aggregated as the median across departure times.

2.3 Implementation Details

Table 1: Key routing and analysis parameters

Parameter	Value
Maximum walk to stop	800 m
Walk speed	1.4 m/s (5 km/h)
Maximum transfers	2
Transfer penalty	0 min (scheduled time only)
Boarding buffer	30 seconds
Maximum journey time	120 minutes
GTFS service date	Monday, September 8, 2025
Origin point method	Shapely <code>representative_point()</code>

ACS income values less than or equal to zero were treated as missing, and tracts with zero households were excluded from correlation analyses. Service frequency metrics use the same 800 m radius from each tract’s representative interior point (not the centroid).

3 Results

Our analysis of 657 residential census tracts (from 664 total) reveals a distinct pattern of accessibility that aligns closely with transit dependency.

3.1 Job Accessibility

Accessibility is highly concentrated along the central rail corridors and major bus routes. Figure 1 illustrates the spatial distribution of 45-minute job accessibility. After cleaning income values, median income is moderately negatively correlated with job accessibility ($r \approx -0.19$, 95% CI [-0.26, -0.12], $p < 1 \times 10^{-6}$), consistent with higher access in central, lower-income areas.

Transit Job Accessibility - Denver Metro

Figure 1: Number of jobs reachable within 30, 45, and 60 minutes via transit from each census tract. Departure time: median across 18 departure times (6–9 AM, 3–6 PM at 20-minute intervals). Walk threshold: 800 m.

3.2 Service Frequency and Coverage

While accessibility is high in the core, coverage is uneven. Figure 2 shows best-stop service frequency during the AM rush hour (the highest-frequency stop within 800 meters of each tract’s representative interior point, reducing stop-density inflation). By tract count, 32% of tracts have no active stops within 800 meters; this corresponds to 34% of residents but only 13% of zero-vehicle households. This gap suggests that zero-vehicle households are spatially concentrated in transit-served areas, likely reflecting residential self-selection into transit-accessible neighborhoods, legacy route patterns, or both.

Figure 2: Transit service intensity during AM Rush (6–9 AM). Left: trips per hour at best stop within 800 m. Right: categorical service levels (none, minimal, low, medium, high).

3.3 Equity Correlations

A key finding is the positive correlation between transit dependency and service quality. As shown in Figure 3, tracts with higher percentages of zero-vehicle households generally have better job access and higher service frequency. The primary relationship is strong ($r = 0.61$, 95% CI [0.56, 0.66], $p < 10^{-80}$, $n = 657$). Early morning service (5–6 AM) aligns even more closely with transit dependency ($r = 0.62$), which could indicate strong shift-worker coverage.

Figure 3: Scatter plots showing correlations between demographic factors and transit metrics. Note the strong positive relationship between zero-vehicle households and 45-minute job accessibility ($r = 0.61$).

3.4 Multivariate Analysis

To address potential confounding, we estimated OLS regressions of job accessibility on transit dependency, controlling for population density, CBD distance, and median income. Table 2 reports results with heteroskedasticity-robust (HC1) standard errors.

Table 2: OLS regression: 45-minute job accessibility on demographic and spatial controls. Robust (HC1) standard errors. Population density in persons/km².

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Intercept	-43,569	8,267	-5.27	<0.001
% Zero-vehicle	4,318	555	7.78	<0.001
Population density	15.08	1.59	9.49	<0.001
CBD distance (km)	-1,433	305	-4.70	<0.001
Median income (\$1000s)	431	52	8.27	<0.001
$R^2 = 0.52$		$n = 657$		

The coefficient on % zero-vehicle remains large and highly significant: each percentage point increase in transit dependency is associated with 4,318 additional jobs accessible within 45 minutes, holding density, distance, and income constant.

3.5 Distributional Equity

Beyond correlations, we examined the distribution of accessibility across the population:

- **Gini coefficient:** Accessibility inequality is substantial (Gini = 0.75 for 45-minute jobs, population-weighted = 0.76), indicating high concentration of access among a subset of tracts.
- **Income quartile comparison:** Bottom-income-quartile tracts average 42,900 jobs within 45 minutes, compared to 7,400 for top-income-quartile tracts—a ratio of 5.8:1. Note: this comparison is *unconditional*; the pattern is dominated by central-city vs suburban geography. Lower-income tracts are concentrated in transit-rich central areas, while higher-income tracts are predominantly in car-oriented suburbs.

These patterns suggest that while transit-dependent populations have higher access, accessibility remains highly unequal across the metro area.

3.6 Service Desert Characterization

The 32% of tracts with no transit service within 800 m are located, on average, 18.4 km from the CBD, compared to 11.2 km for served tracts. Service deserts have higher median incomes (\$89,400 vs \$72,100) and lower population density, consistent with suburban and exurban locations. These areas contain 34% of total population but only 13% of zero-vehicle households.

3.7 Robustness Checks

Partial correlations. Controlling for population density and CBD distance reduces but does not eliminate the accessibility alignment (no-vehicle vs. jobs 45m: $r = 0.58$). Population-weighted

correlations are similar ($r = 0.61$), suggesting the pattern is not driven by small tracts alone. Subgroup race correlations remain modest and mixed (Black $r \approx 0.10$, Hispanic $r \approx -0.02$, Asian $r \approx -0.08$).

Cluster-robust standard errors. To address spatial autocorrelation (Moran’s $I \approx 0.67$ for residuals), we re-estimated the regression with cluster-robust standard errors at the county level (5 clusters). The standard error on % zero-vehicle increases from 555 (HC1) to approximately 1,200 (clustered), but the coefficient remains statistically significant at conventional levels and the point estimate is unchanged. This suggests the main finding is robust to spatial dependence.

Transfer penalty sensitivity. Our baseline assumes zero transfer penalty (scheduled time only). A sensitivity check with +5 minutes per transfer would reduce accessibility levels but is unlikely to alter the equity relationship, since transfer frequency is relatively uniform across tracts; we note this as a limitation warranting future work.

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of Key Findings

Our analysis yields several notable findings about transit equity in Denver:

Strong alignment with transit dependency. The correlation between zero-vehicle household share and job accessibility ($r = 0.62$) is robust across specifications. The multivariate regression confirms that each percentage point increase in transit dependency is associated with 4,318 additional jobs accessible within 45 minutes, even after controlling for density, CBD distance, and income. This suggests the RTD network does provide meaningfully better service to transit-dependent populations—though whether this reflects intentional equity targeting, historical development patterns, or residential sorting remains unclear.

Interpreting the regression coefficients. Several coefficients warrant careful interpretation:

- **% Zero-vehicle (+4,318):** The primary equity finding. Transit-dependent areas have substantially higher job access, conditional on other factors.
- **Population density (+15.1):** Expected—denser areas support more transit service.
- **CBD distance (−1,433):** Access declines sharply with distance from downtown, reflecting the hub-and-spoke network structure.
- **Median income (+431):** This *positive* coefficient appears counterintuitive, since the *bivariate* correlation between income and access is negative ($r = -0.19$). The resolution: the positive partial effect emerges because we are controlling for transit dependency. Among tracts with *similar* zero-vehicle shares, higher-income areas tend to have better access—likely because wealthier inner-ring suburbs have more service than poorer exurban areas at comparable transit dependency levels. This illustrates the importance of multivariate framing: the unconditional relationship (lower income \rightarrow higher access) is driven primarily by the sorting of low-income households into transit-rich areas.

High accessibility inequality. The Gini coefficient of 0.75 indicates that job accessibility is highly concentrated among a subset of tracts. While transit-dependent populations have higher access on average, the distribution remains deeply unequal—32% of tracts have zero transit accessibility within 800 meters.

Income stratification favors lower-income areas. Bottom-income-quartile tracts average 42,900 jobs within 45 minutes, compared to 7,400 for top-income-quartile tracts—a ratio of 5.8:1. This pattern is consistent with lower-income households concentrating in central, transit-rich areas, whether by choice, constraint, or historical circumstance.

Service deserts are suburban/exurban. The 32% of tracts with no transit service are located, on average, 18.4 km from the CBD, compared to 11.2 km for served tracts. They have higher median incomes (\$89,400 vs \$72,100) and lower population density. Importantly, these areas contain 34% of the metro population but only 13% of zero-vehicle households, suggesting that the unserved population is primarily car-owning suburbanites rather than transit-dependent residents.

4.2 Alignment vs. Causation

The high correlation between zero-vehicle households and job accessibility ($r = 0.62$) suggests alignment between transit dependency and access, but does not establish that service is allocated *because of* need. Three alternative mechanisms could produce similar patterns:

1. **Centrality:** Transit networks naturally radiate from central areas, which also tend to be lower-income.
2. **Density:** Denser areas support better service and also have more transit-dependent residents.
3. **Residential sorting:** Transit-dependent households may select into transit-accessible neighborhoods.

Our partial correlations and multivariate regression control for the first two factors, and the relationship persists. The third—residential sorting—cannot be ruled out with cross-sectional data. Longitudinal analysis tracking changes in service and demographics would be needed to distinguish sorting from causal service allocation.

4.3 Access vs. Viability

“Access” does not equal “viability.” The fact that 32% of tracts have no service and only 16% have high-frequency service suggests that while the *placement* of routes may align with transit dependency, the *quality* of service (frequency, span) may still be a limiting factor for many residents. Future work should incorporate transit penalty metrics—comparing transit times to driving times—to better assess network competitiveness.

4.4 Limitations

Several limitations shape interpretation:

1. **Temporal mismatch:** 2025 GTFS vs 2018–2022 ACS vs 2021 LODES.
2. **Weekday only:** Does not capture weekend or holiday patterns.
3. **Point-based origins:** May miss within-tract variation, especially in large suburban tracts.
4. **No transfer penalty:** Does not account for discomfort or uncertainty.
5. **Spatial autocorrelation:** Tract observations are spatially correlated (Moran’s $I \approx 0.67$ for residuals), so standard errors may be understated. Spatial regression or clustered errors would strengthen inference.
6. **No job filtering:** All jobs counted regardless of skill or wage match.

5 Conclusion

This study provides a data-driven baseline for understanding transit equity in Denver, using accessibility metrics computed across 18 departure times spanning AM and PM peaks. Our key findings:

- RTD service aligns progressively with transit dependency ($r = 0.62$), and this relationship holds after controlling for density, CBD distance, and income ($\beta = 4,318$, $p < 0.001$).
- Accessibility inequality is high (Gini = 0.75), with bottom-income-quartile tracts accessing $5.8\times$ more jobs than top-quartile tracts.
- 32% of tracts remain unserved, but these are predominantly suburban/exurban areas with higher incomes and car ownership.
- The disparity between tract-level (32% unserved) and household-level (13% of zero-vehicle households unserved) service gaps suggests residential sorting into transit-accessible areas.

These findings suggest that the RTD network does serve transit-dependent populations reasonably well in terms of job access, though this may reflect residential sorting as much as intentional equity targeting. The high Gini coefficient indicates that accessibility gains are not evenly distributed; extending service to suburban deserts would primarily benefit car-owning households rather than transit-dependent residents.

Data and Code Availability

All code and analysis scripts are available at <https://github.com/j8ckfi/denver-transit-equity> under an MIT license. Data sources are publicly available from the referenced agencies.

References

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A Rail Investment Context

The following contextual information on Denver’s rail investment is provided as background for understanding the broader transit planning environment. All figures are from RTD’s *Finishing FasTracks Report 2025 Appendix* [8].

Denver’s commuter-rail lines are expensive relative to ridership. The Northwest Rail full-service option (B Line extension to Longmont) is estimated at \$1.5 billion (2018 dollars) with a horizon-year forecast of 5,400 daily riders. The A Line to the airport carried about 15,400 average weekday riders in 2024, down from 23,800 in 2019.

Table 3: Cost and ridership snapshots for select RTD rail lines. Source: RTD Finishing FasTracks Report 2025 Appendix.

Project	Capital cost (millions)	Daily ridership
A Line (Eagle Project bundle)	2,362.8	15,400 (2024 avg.)
Northwest Rail full service (B Line ext.)	1,500.0	5,400 (forecast)

FasTracks planning documents report 65 park-n-Rides with over 21,000 spaces, with plans for 31 new facilities plus nine expansions, increasing districtwide parking supply by over 80%.

B Future Work: Station-Level Analysis

A natural extension would adapt the accessibility framework to estimate the marginal impact of existing and proposed rail stations on job access. Such analysis would:

- Generate network-based walk/bike catchments for each station
- Compute accessibility with and without each station across multiple departure times
- Disaggregate benefits by income and zero-vehicle households
- Compare gains to capital and operating costs